

**2023-DL.3.2.2-REFINED DRAFT GUIDELINES FOR BROILER WELFARE
ASSESSMENT BASED ON INDICATORS IDENTIFIED IN ACTIVITY 2 AND
FEEDBACK ON ITS APPLICATION ON FIELD IN TEN BROILER FARMS**

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1. Definitions

Item: A welfare requisite to assess, included in the Classyfarm system, which can be:

- **Legal requirement:** a requisite of the EU legislation to be assessed during the official controls. Example: Directive 98/58 EC, Annex, Paragraph 10: “Temperature, relative air humidity [...] must be kept within limits which are not harmful to the animals”
- **Additional requirement:** Conditions that are not legally mandatory but supported by literature in improving the welfare of farmed animals. Example: maintenance of drinkers, litter quality, environmental enrichments.

Indicator: an indicator is an occurrence, observation, record or measurement which has a proven relationship with the requirement (legal requirements and others) which can be:

- **Iceberg indicator:** indicator reflecting major welfare issues in an integrative manner in order to enable an initial overview of the welfare state.
- **Animal-based indicator (ABI):** a response of an animal or an effect on an animal used to assess its welfare. It can be taken directly on the animal or indirectly and includes the use of animal records. Example: huddling as ABI of cold stress and panting as ABI of heat stress.
- **Resource-based indicator (RBI):** an evaluation of a feature of the environment in which the animal is kept or to which it is exposed. Example: environmental temperature, humidity.
- **Management-based indicator (MBI):** an evaluation of what the animal unit manager or stockperson does, and which management processes or tools are used. Example: protocol for activation of the ventilation system (*EURCAW-Poultry-SFA, 2020*).

Method for the assessment (= method): a form of evaluation of the indicators that might be used in the frame of the verification of the requirements (legal requirements and others). Example: examine groups of birds at up to 5 well-distributed locations. If birds are panting, count out 100 birds (do not disturb them and leave them sitting where they are) and estimate how many of the 100 birds are panting.

Classyfarm platform: Italian national platform able to categorize, through an algorithm, the animal welfare risk level of farms.

2. Introduction

In 2018, the Italian Ministry of Health commissioned the Istituto Zooprofilattico Sperimentale della Lombardia e dell'Emilia Romagna (IZSLER) to develop a national platform, named Classyfarm, that categorizes, through a scoring system, the risk arising from farm animal welfare in the context of veterinary public health inspections. The sections of interest are six: animal welfare, biosecurity, health parameters, animal nutrition, antimicrobial consumption and lesions detected at slaughterhouse.

Animal welfare sections have been developed for most of the farmed animal species and for different rearing systems aimed not only at supporting official controls on implementation of animal welfare legislation, but also to collect farms data at national level. For this, checklists and guidelines for their correct usage were drafted.

In broilers, the first checklist and guidelines were developed in 2019, taking into consideration the legal requirements of Council Directive 98/58/EC of 20 July 1998 concerning the protection of animals kept for farming purposes and Council Directive 2007/43/EC of 28 June 2007 laying down minimum rules for the protection of chickens kept for meat production and how to check compliance of the legal requirements through indicators and methods reported by *EURCAW-Poultry-SFA (2020a, 2020b)*. During 2023, focusing on animal welfare, an Expert Knowledge Elicitation (EKE) was organized to collect the opinion of ten Italian poultry veterinarians from different working environments (Istituti Zooprofilattici, Universities, official veterinarians and private practitioners). The experts were asked to rate the relevance of the items included in the checklist in terms of their impact on broilers welfare and the certainty of their judgement in order to weight the items.

The checklist on the welfare of the broiler foresees the assessment of a total of 47 items, 40 items are legal requirements while 7 are additional requirements. The items are classified in different risk areas:

- Area A – “Management”; This area includes the assessment of items through MBIs.
- Area B – “Equipment and facilities”. This area includes the assessment of items through RBIs which the corresponding non-compliance category can be reported.
- Area C – “Animal – based measures” This area includes the assessment of items through ABIs.
- Area “Emergency management and alarm systems” This area considers certain environmental factors that in the event of a major hazard situation, could make a difference in safeguarding health and welfare of the animals (e.g. item 37 – Alarm system, ANNEX I).

Relevance was scored in a 6-point scoring scale (from 0 being “negligible impact on welfare” to 5 being “very high impact on welfare”) while the certainty of the judgement was scored in a 3-point scale (from 1 “low certainty” to 3 “high certainty”).

Outcomes of EKE were used to ‘weigh’ the different items, so that a score was assigned to each item according to its potential impact on animal welfare and the checklist was structured in order to mark one of the two or three possible answers for each Item assessed being:

- Insufficient where minimum requirements are not met
- Acceptable where minimum requirements are fulfilled
- Optimal where it is possible to highlight conditions exceeding minimum requirements.

The Classyfarm tool can be filled directly on farm via mobile/browser application, thus avoiding the use of paper sheets. All data are then directly transferred to the Classyfarm platform, which automatically processes data and generate a PDF document (report) showing the percentage score obtained for each Area and the total welfare score of the farm, reflecting the risk in terms of animal welfare, such as evaluated by this system. The dedicated platform algorithm elaborates the data collected on farm, to provide a percentage corresponding to the risk level related to animal welfare where 0 indicates a high welfare risk and 100 indicates a low welfare risk. Specifically, the thresholds of the total welfare score are as follows: a score up to 59% is to be considered as poor, from 60 to 80% medium and above 80% good in terms of welfare. Contributions to the total welfare score come from 25% final score in Area A, 25% final score in Area B and 50% final score in Area C as reported in *Ginestreti et al., (2020)*. In this sense, outcomes of ABIs have a greater impact on the total welfare score than RBIs and MBIs. The “Emergency management and alarm systems” area score is separated from the total welfare score.

The output of Classyfarm is represented through interactive dashboards. These, provide results on welfare scores at both individual (single farm) and aggregated level (national, regional or local group of farms), giving users an overview and the opportunity to compare their farm’s welfare scores with the national and regional or local average ones. However, for broilers reports and dashboards are not yet available and therefore it was not possible to verify their functioning and the welfare scores given by the Classyfarm system.

This document, attached to the Classyfarm checklists and guidelines, provide a preliminary feedback about time required and the feasibility of the welfare assessment in broiler farms. In addition, ABIs and associated methods derived from the ongoing work of the EURCAW Poultry -SFA are considered, with the aim of integrating them in the near future within the welfare assessment system for broilers

currently in use. These preliminary results will be integrated with the scores provided by the Classyfarm IT platform as soon as they are available.

3. Methodology

3.1 Preliminary work

In order to perform visits to broiler farms, it was necessary to carry out some preliminary work. First, checklist and guidelines text have been updated to the latest available version, dating from 2022, and translated into English language, so that it could be shared with EU Member States. Subsequently, the Italian checklist had to be entered into the Classyfarm platform. To do this, it was necessary to manually enter the title, description and answers of each item on the checklist in “create new questionnaire template” Classyfarm section. For each possible answer, the score resulting from the EKE was entered: this procedure results essential, as it will allow the platform to calculate the welfare scores. The same work was carried out with the translated checklist, with the aim of obtaining evaluation outputs in English language.

3.2 Inspections in broiler farms

With the aim of testing the Classyfarm checklist on broilers, ten farm visits were conducted. These have been carried out, always by the same two people, in Italy between July and November 2023, specifically in the Lombardy region (Brescia).

3.2.1 List of equipment needed

Before carrying out the assessment, inspectors should be equipped with:

- Broiler welfare checklists (one for each visited house) or tablet (if filled in directly on farm through the mobile application).
- Clean and appropriate clothing and footwear (one for each house)
- Devices for measuring environmental parameters (CO₂, NH₃, relative humidity and environmental temperature)
- A5 – A6 size sheets of black paper for measuring dust level (two for each section of the house)
- Laser distance meter and/or measuring tape
- Digital light meter

It is advisable to check that the digital equipment for measuring light and environmental parameters are calibrated according to the manufacturing instructions.

3.2.2 Practical information

Upon arrival, after complying with the farm biosecurity procedures, the visit begins.

The first part of the data retrieval is carried out in the office, where the following information is collected:

- farm data (housing system, number and size of house, number of animals at the time of the inspection for each house, and technical documentation regarding the housing system).
- data records (e.g. animals' age, mortality, veterinary treatments, water and feed consumption, *fig.1*).

1)

2)

Figure 1. 1) Water and feed consumption control unit. 2) Feed consumption with weighing-silos informatic tool. (IZSLER)

Before entering the house, the proper functioning of the control units, when present, is checked. In particular, it is required to test the functioning of:

- Control units for monitoring environmental parameters (CO₂, NH₃, relative humidity and environmental temperature)
- Control units of ventilation system (*fig.2*)
- Light programme control units (*fig.3*)
- Alarm system
- Power generator
- Emergency water system

This preliminary information gives a general overview of the microclimatic conditions and light levels of the houses that are then verified once inside.

Figure 2. Example of ventilation system control unit (IZSLER)

Figure 3. Example of light programme control unit (IZSLER)

3.2.3 Sequence of the visit

Checklist: Area A – Management

The first area of the checklist (Area A - Management) includes twelve items (see ANNEX I), assessing compliance with current European legislation (Council Directive 98/58/EC of 20 July 1998 and Council Directive 2007/43/EC of 28 June 2007) and evaluates MBIs implemented on farm, such as: training of keeper, management of sick or injured animals, availability of feed prior to slaughter, drinker maintenance and litter management. The items of this area can be partially assessed during the interview with the farmer and subsequently confirmed with an inspection inside the house, in particular with the transect walk method, which allows the welfare condition of the animals and the maintenance of structures and litter to be checked.

Checklist: Area B – Equipment and facilities

The second area of the checklist (Area B – Equipment and facilities), including sixteen items (ANNEX I) of which twelve are assessing the compliance with current European legislation (Council Directive 98/58/EC of 20 July 1998 and Council Directive 2007/43/EC of 28 June 2007) about the adequacy of facilities and equipment, such as minimum requirements for stocking density and environmental conditions inside the house. Four items contain additional requirement (item 15 “Environmental enrichments, 27 “control unit for monitoring environmental parameters” 28 and 29 “daily water and feed consumption”). In this Area, some items are exclusive to farms with a derogation $>33\text{kg/m}^2$. For the purpose of assessing dust levels, sheets were placed at the beginning of the inspection inside the houses.

Checklist: Area C – Animal based measures

The third area of the checklist (Area C – Animal – based indicators, including four items (ANNEX I) of which three are those assessing the compliance with current European legislation regarding mutilations (Council Directive 98/58/EC of 20 July 1998 (Item 30, 31 and 32 “authorisations”, “surgical interventions” and “timing and methods”) and one is item 33 “weekly mortality rate”, an indirect ABI that is an additional requirement. In addition to these, the transect walk method was carried out to check the general welfare state of the animals through the use of direct ABIs.

Checklist: Area – Emergency management and alarm systems

This area considers certain environmental factors that do not affect directly animals' welfare, but in the event of a major hazard situation (e.g. water or electrical faults) could play a key role in safeguarding the bird's health. These include the specific requirements specified by the Council Directive 2007/43/EC of 28 June 2007 for farms with a derogation $> 33\text{kg/m}^2$: item 45 "notification and documentation" and for farms with a derogation $> 39 - 42\text{ kg/m}^2$ item 46 "criteria for the use of increased stocking density". All these items are assessed at the beginning of the visit, before entering the houses.

4. Results

The ten broiler farms inspected had a higher stocking density of a maximum of 39kg/m^2 , since the keepers complies with the requirements set out in directive 2007/43/EC.

The total duration of each inspection made was in average 70 min, of which 30 min for inspections of official documentation and central control units and 40 min for the inspections performed inside the house.

Overall, of ten carried out, 20 Items out of 470 assessed (4.2% of total) were scored "insufficient" by evaluators. The items that were most subject to answer variation were the following: Item 11 "drinker maintenance", 12 "litter quality", 18 "infirmary" and 33 "average weekly mortality". In particular:

- two out ten farms didn't comply with the minimum requirements regarding the maintenance of drinkers, which were leaking water ("insufficient" score). Seven farms obtained the "acceptable" score, which requires that drinkers are not clogged and do not leak water while the "optimal" score, which requires the written procedure for when and how the drinkers should be maintained, was achieved by one farm.
- the same two farms that had leaking drinkers (2 out 10), were given poor quality ("insufficient") on litter quality which presented a very wet and non-friable litter (which were given a moisture/friability score of less than or equal to 5), six farms obtained "acceptable" (with scores between 6 and 8): the litter was well maintained, with small ridges visible beneath the drinking line, and two farms had well-dried and crumbly bedding on the drinking line and therefore obtained "optimal".
- five farms out ten did not have an infirmary or at least an area that could be used as an infirmary when needed.

- the answers given to the item 33, referring to the ABI “average weekly mortality”, were “insufficient” in two farms (with weekly mortality thresholds higher than 1%), “acceptable” in 4 farms (weekly mortality thresholds between 0.6% and 1%) and “optimal” in four farms (weekly mortality thresholds lower than 0.6%).

Nine out ten farms did not have any environmental enrichment present inside the house (additional requirement) and all farms inspected were given the score “optimal” in item 31 “Mutilations”. This means that in all the farms inspected the birds did not present any type of mutilation, which is classical for broiler chickens.

In total, the “optimal” answer (in which the minimum requirements are exceeded) was assigned 97 times (44,1%) out of the total 220 items assessed for which an optimal answer has been set. Most of the optimal answers were given to mutilations (items belonging to Area C) and automation, alarm and monitoring systems for light and environmental parameters, which are items belonging to the emergency management and alarm system area.

The results of the transect walk method, performed during the assessment of Area A item 5 “management of sick or injured animals” have been encouraging, since this method provides practical help to official inspectors to evaluate welfare indicators such as lameness, immobility, back dirtiness, sickness, agonizing or dead birds.

5. Discussion

The welfare checklist for broilers that was evaluated appears to be well structured and easy to follow during the field visit and they were all filled out directly on farm, via the app.

Sheets to check the level of dustiness of the animal housing environment were placed at the beginning of the inspection inside the house and collected at the end of the inspection. 40 minutes was sufficient to get an idea of the dust levels inside the houses; however, holding the sheets for longer periods (e.g. 2 – 3 h as described by *EURCAW Poultry - SFA*®, 2022) would probably raise the level of reliability of the dust sheet test.

Items regarding lighting parameters (items 24-25) can be difficult to assess, especially if digital light meter is not available and/or the farm does not have lighting control units for managing light period and light intensity. Therefore, it is recommended to use a calibrated digital light meter and measure different zones (at least 5) that are representative of the light distribution of the entire house and taking into account that the light intensity of natural light is greater than that of artificial light (*EURCAW Poultry -SFA, 2020c*) Also, in the case of length or surface measurements (e.g. measuring a feeder) it is recommended to use laser distance meter as they allow easier, faster and more accurate measure.

Although some ABIs have been suggested by the *EURCAW-Poultry-SFA (2020a, 2020b)* and *Welfare Quality*® (2009), only two are currently included in the Classyfarm animal welfare checklist (mutilations and average weekly mortality) that was tested here. In fact, the checklist only focuses on a single iceberg indicator which is the average weekly mortality and collect data from indicators that are easier to assess (RBIs, MBIs), in order to obtain large databases of information throughout the Country. There is then a necessity to integrate in the present checklist some direct ABIs that can be effective for a more complete evaluation of bird's welfare on farm.

As far as farmed poultry are concerned, assessing ABIs in large numbers of animals during field visit might be time consuming, as several indicators would require handling (and thus specific training by the assessor) and more time for the evaluations. On the other hand, ABIs are a direct reflect of the welfare of the animals. The difficult epidemiological situation related to the spread of the HP Avian Influenza did not allow us to evaluate additional ABIs measured through birds handling. Therefore, what can be recommended is the use of the transect walk method to assess several welfare indicators (e.g. difficulties in walking, injured birds, undersized animals) without handling birds. The transect method was carried out at the time of the assessment of item 5 "treatment of sick or injured animals and culling". This method distinguishes individuals with visible severe welfare issues and provides a quick estimation of general flock health and welfare status giving, as described in *EURCAW-Poultry-SFA, (2020b)*. In this sense, the addition of several ABIs assessed during transect walk within the broiler welfare checklist will certainly help to better evaluate the welfare status of the birds.

The checklist tested allow to collect feasible items in a reasonable timing (70 min on average). Within the Classyfarm platform the main outputs (reports and dashboards, as already shown for laying hens) will be available in the near future. These will be helpful to quantify and compare the welfare level of a farm or a group of farm vs the rest of the population inside a member state but also in between Member States.

6. Conclusions

The welfare assessment of broiler welfare can be carried out on-farm by using the provided checklist, which includes MBIs, RBIs and ABIs.

Currently, the Classyfarm checklist for the welfare assessment of broiler includes only two ABIs to be assessed on farm. As already described by *EURCAW-Poultry-SFA, (2020b)* the transect walk method is useful for determining different ABIs like lameness, immobility, back dirtiness, sickness, agonizing or

dead birds without handling the birds. Therefore, it is likely that more ABIs should be included into the Classyfarm welfare checklist in the future, to have a more valid assessment of the welfare of the birds.

Although the main outputs of the platform are not yet available, they will have the following purposes:

- support during official inspections
- comparison between farms in terms of animal welfare risk. In addition, this information could be useful to appropriately target preventive interventions on the main risk factors, thus improving the living conditions of the animals.

These data will be important to improve animal welfare and safeguard the agri-food sector in a sustainable way, in line with the European Farm to Fork Strategy.

This guidance, already developed through an app and in English, could be used to monitor welfare of broiler chickens through Europe. Moreover, the use of a single monitoring system through European countries could help getting a picture of welfare trends in Europe, thus better defining what has improved and what still needs to be improved.

7. References

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